

The Impact of School Facilities and Infrastructure Availability on Educational Services at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung

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Abstract: The objective of this research is to determine the positive and significant impact of the availability of school facilities and infrastructure on the quality of learning services at SMP N 4 Tarutung. The methodology employed in this study is quantitative with inferential statistics. The population consists of 231 students from grades IX and VIII at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung, and a sample of 57 was selected using random sampling techniques. Data was collected through a closed-ended questionnaire consisting of 42 items. The data analysis reveals a positive and significant influence of the availability of school facilities and infrastructure on the quality of learning services at SMP N 4 Tarutung: 1.) Analysis prerequisites: a) For positive influence testing, the value of $r_{xy} = 0.681$ is greater than $r_{table} (\alpha = 0.05, n = 57) = 0.226$, indicating a positive influence between variable X and variable Y. b) For the significance of the relationship, the calculated t value is 6.899, which is greater than $t_{table} (\alpha = 0.05, df = n - 2 = 55) = 2.000$, indicating a significant relationship between variable X and variable Y. 2.) Influence testing: a) Regression equation testing yielded the regression equation $\hat{Y} = 3.252 + 0.782X$. b) The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 46.4%. 3.) Hypothesis testing using the F test showed $F_{count} > F_{table}$ specifically $47.593 > 4.00$. Therefore, H_a is accepted, and H_0 is rejected.

Keywords: Availability of School Facilities and Infrastructure, Learning Services.

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Introduction

The success of an educational system relies heavily on various supporting components, one of which is the availability of facilities and infrastructure essential for the continuity of learning in schools. The availability of school facilities and infrastructure is a crucial asset for enhancing the quality of student learning, and thus, these facilities must be utilized optimally to achieve the desired objectives as planned. Successful learning in schools is supported by the effective and efficient use of all educational facilities available.

Essentially, learning facilities in schools refer to the equipment and resources used during the educational process, such as buildings, classrooms, desks, chairs, and teaching tools and media. Learning infrastructure, on the other hand, includes amenities that indirectly support the learning process, such as school grounds, gardens, canteens, parking areas, restrooms, and so forth. The presence of these facilities and infrastructure ensures that the learning process is well-directed and achieves its goal of providing professional services related to educational resources, enabling effective and efficient learning. A well-maintained school environment can make students feel more comfortable and motivated, leading to better learning outcomes (Manullang and

Silitonga, 2022). When various necessary facilities are available during the teaching and learning process, they reinforce students' learning by clarifying information and concepts being studied.

The availability of facilities and infrastructure in schools can enhance teaching enthusiasm, which can be viewed from two dimensions: as a process of delivering instructional material and as a process of managing the environment to stimulate students' learning. In this regard, adequate school facilities and infrastructure have a significant impact on the success of the learning process. This demonstrates that the availability of these resources greatly influences the achievement of effective learning and affects the quality of learning services.

Learning services refer to the support provided to students to help them develop positive attitudes and habits. These services can be seen as an indicator of the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process, reflecting the performance of both teachers and students. Quality learning is achieved when teachers successfully transform students' attitudes, behaviors, and skills. Providing high-quality learning services is challenging, as it involves various issues related to educational services, one of which is the availability of facilities and infrastructure. Thus, the availability of facilities and infrastructure can create a conducive environment for

both students and educators. Since these resources play a crucial role in contributing optimally to the learning process, their adequacy is essential for improving learning services. With sufficient and standard-compliant facilities and infrastructure, students' needs are met, enabling them to learn more diligently.

Research Methods

The research method employed in this study is quantitative with inferential statistics. According to Sugiyono, inferential statistics are techniques used to analyze sample data and apply the results to the population. This type of statistics is suitable when the sample is drawn from a clearly defined population. Therefore, in this study, to determine the effect of variable X on variable Y, a quantitative method with inferential statistics is used.

Discussion

a. Learning Services

Service is a voluntary action by one party to another, aimed solely at assisting or fulfilling the needs of the other party voluntarily. The consumer receiving the service will then assess whether they will remain loyal to the service provider. According to Tjiptono, as cited by Khairul, service refers to any action offered by one party to another, which is essentially intangible (not physically manifest) and does not result in ownership of something. According to Gagne, learning is a carefully organized arrangement of events aimed at achieving personal success for the learner. Therefore, learning is a process undertaken to provide instruction to students so that they receive quality education from learning sources, with the goal of ensuring effective learning that leads to personal success for the students. Learning services refer to the process of preparing the needs of students by the school through various educational activities that utilize school facilities to enhance students' cognitive, affective, and psychomotor abilities. This process aims to achieve school goals effectively and efficiently. Learning services can also be defined as activities provided by teachers in educational settings, which may include organizing or arranging the environment around students to encourage and foster learning activities, and to support behavioral changes and student development.

Based on the above opinions, it can be concluded that learning services refer to the efforts or processes undertaken by teachers to provide educational services to learners (students). This involves every action or activity that teachers offer to students, with a focus on the quality of the learning interactions. In other words, a teacher's role includes not only delivering instruction but also providing stimulation and support to students experiencing difficulties in the learning process. This is aimed at helping students optimally achieve their academic potential.

In this context, teachers act as guides in providing learning services within the domain of educational guidance, addressing students' learning issues. Effective implementation of these learning services in educational guidance enables students to develop themselves optimally. Therefore, the quality of learning services can be assessed by comparing students' perceptions of the services they receive with the actual services provided, to determine whether these services meet the expected standards.

According to Berry as cited in Mulyadi, the measurement of student satisfaction with learning services is based on the following indicators:

1. **Tangibles:** This includes aspects of service related to the use of physical objects, such as instructional tools and learning media in the classroom.
2. **Reliability:** This pertains to the dependability of a teacher, which includes arriving on time, employing various engaging teaching methods, providing opportunities for students to ask questions and express opinions, and effectively managing the classroom environment.
3. **Responsiveness:** This refers to the teacher's ability to respond to students' issues both within and outside the learning context.
4. **Assurance:** This involves the teacher's ability to instill confidence in students through demonstrated mastery of the subject matter, thereby fostering a sense of trust and assurance in the students.
5. **Empathy:** In psychological terms, empathy refers to the mental state that enables an individual to share and understand the feelings and experiences of others.

Based on the expert opinions above, it can be concluded that the quality of learning services is assessed by:

1. **Teacher Reliability in Providing Learning Services:** This refers to the teacher's ability to deliver services to students promptly, accurately, on schedule (as promised), and satisfactorily.
2. **Teacher Responsiveness in Providing Learning Services:** This denotes the teacher's willingness to assist and respond to students' needs quickly, accurately, and sincerely.
3. **Service Assurance in Learning:** This involves the teacher's ability to instill confidence and trust in students by demonstrating discipline and responsibility in their role as educators.
4. **Empathy in Learning Services:** This is defined as the teacher's readiness to understand students' problems, difficulties, and needs, provide personal attention, facilitate communication, and offer wholehearted and sincere service to all students.

b. Availability of Facilities and Infrastructure

Availability comes from the word "sedia," which means ready or preparedness. According to the *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia* (KBBI), availability refers to the readiness of a resource (such as personnel, goods, capital, or budget) to be used or operated within a specified time. The availability of facilities and infrastructure is crucial and a fundamental requirement in the teaching and learning process, as their presence encourages teachers to utilize them effectively.

Mulyasa defines facilities and infrastructure separately. Educational facilities are the equipment and supplies directly used to support the educational process, particularly teaching and learning, such as whiteboards, markers, erasers, stationery, books, and teaching media. In contrast, infrastructure refers to the amenities that indirectly support the educational or teaching process within an educational institution, such as buildings, classrooms, playgrounds, school gardens, access roads to the school, and so forth (Ariawan, 2020).

The availability of facilities and infrastructure is defined as everything that can facilitate and streamline the execution of

various tasks. This includes physical objects that can assist and expedite these efforts. In this context, the availability of facilities and infrastructure can be equated with the resources available in schools. Each educational institution must be equipped with facilities such as furniture, educational equipment, teaching media, books, and other learning resources, consumables, and other necessary items to support orderly learning processes. Educational institutions also require infrastructure, including land, classrooms, administrative offices, teacher rooms, administrative offices, libraries, and other spaces necessary for supporting continuous learning.

According to Indonesian Government Regulation No. 57 of 2021, Article 25, concerning Standards for Facilities and Infrastructure, the minimum criteria for facilities and infrastructure required in educational institutions must support effective learning, ensure safety, be accessible to individuals with disabilities, and be environmentally friendly. Facilities and infrastructure must be available at educational institutions and tailored to the needs of each level, stage, and type of education.

According to Nawawi, as cited in Isnawardatul Bararah, educational infrastructure in schools is classified into two types: infrastructure that is directly used for the teaching and learning process, and infrastructure that is not directly utilized in the teaching and learning process. The infrastructure directly used in the teaching and learning process includes theory classrooms, libraries, skill practice rooms, and laboratories. When linked to the standards for educational facilities and infrastructure as outlined in Indonesian Minister of Education Regulation No. 24 of 2007, the facilities that directly enhance learning services are classrooms, libraries, laboratories, and play/sports rooms.

A detailed explanation of the directly used educational infrastructure is as follows:

1. Classroom: These are the places where learning takes place. In classrooms, instruction can be both theoretical and practical. Practical instruction can occur in the classroom if it does not require specialized equipment and can be easily accommodated within the classroom setting. Classrooms have facilities that allow adequate lighting for reading books and to provide views to the outside. Classrooms have adequate doors so that students and teachers can leave the room immediately if danger occurs, and can be locked properly when not in use.
2. The library room is a place where books are stored and read. There teachers and students can obtain information from various types of library materials by reading, observing, listening, and at the same time as a place for staff to manage the library. The library room is equipped with windows to provide adequate lighting for reading books. The library room is located in a part of the school/madrasah which is easy to reach.
3. Science laboratory room, the science laboratory room is equipped with facilities to provide adequate lighting for reading books and observing experimental objects, clean water is available and equipped with complete facilities.
4. The playground/exercise area functions as an area for play, exercise, physical education, ceremonies and extracurricular activities. Some playgrounds are planted with green trees. The play/exercise area is placed in a place that will cause the least

disruption to the learning process in the classroom. The playground/exercise area is not used for parking.

In the book *Introduction to School Facility and Infrastructure Management*, Irjus Indrawan argues that, in relation to the teaching and learning process, facilities can be categorized into:

- a. Teaching Tools: These are tools used directly in the teaching and learning process. Examples include books, instructional aids, stationery, and practical tools.
- b. Instructional Aids: These are educational aids that can take the form of models or objects designed to concretize abstract learning material. Instructional aids help make abstract concepts more tangible, facilitating easier comprehension for students.
- c. Learning Media: These are educational resources that serve as intermediaries in the teaching and learning process, aiming to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of achieving educational goals. There are three types of teaching media: visual, auditory, and audiovisual.

It can be concluded that facilities refer to the learning equipment used directly during the learning process. These facilities include furniture, educational tools/teaching aids, educational media/teaching media, and other necessary supplies. Meanwhile, infrastructure refers to the basic facilities required to support the functioning of a school, such as classrooms, libraries, science laboratories, administrative offices, teachers' rooms, administrative offices, prayer rooms, counseling rooms, health units, student organization rooms, restrooms, storage rooms, circulation spaces, and play/sports areas, all of which are standardized by the Ministry of National Education Regulation. Among these, classrooms, libraries, science laboratories, and play/sports areas are the infrastructure directly used in the teaching and learning process.

Based on the research conducted with students at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung, the discussion of the research findings is as follows:

First, the distribution of students' responses regarding the availability of school facilities and infrastructure indicates an impact on the learning services at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung. The availability of school facilities and infrastructure includes indicators such as the availability of teaching tools, learning media, classrooms, libraries, science laboratories, and play/sports areas. With the availability of these facilities and infrastructure, it is expected to enhance the learning services at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung. This enhancement is reflected in the indicators of the reliability of teachers in providing learning services, the responsiveness of teachers in delivering these services, assurance in the provision of learning services, and empathy in the learning services provided.

Second, from the prerequisite analysis test, which examines whether there is a positive relationship between variable X and variable Y, the calculated value (r) is 0.681, compared to the critical value r_{table} for a 5% error rate and a confidence interval (CI) of 95% (100%-5%) for $n = 55$, which is 0.226. The comparison shows that $r_{calculated} > r_{table}$, i.e., $0.681 > 0.226$. This indicates a positive relationship between variable X and variable Y, specifically a positive effect of the availability of school facilities and infrastructure on learning services at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung.

Third, from the prerequisite analysis test, which examines whether there is a significant relationship between variable X and variable Y, the calculated t-value (t-calculated) is 6.899, compared to the critical t-value (t-table) for a 5% error rate and degrees of freedom ($n-2 = 55$), which is 2.000. The comparison shows that $t\text{-calculated} > t\text{-table}$, i.e., $6.899 > 2.000$. This indicates a significant relationship between variable X and variable Y, specifically a significant relationship between the availability of school facilities and infrastructure and learning services at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung.

Fourth, from the regression analysis, it was found that: a) The regression equation is $\hat{Y} = "3.252" + "0.782"X$. This equation indicates that, with a constant of "3.252," each increase in the availability of school facilities and infrastructure will improve learning services at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung by 0.782. b) The determination coefficient test (r^2) yielded a value of 0.464. From this determination value (r^2), it can be inferred that the percentage contribution of the availability of school facilities and infrastructure to learning services at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung is 46.4%. Thus, 53.6% is influenced by other variables, which may include factors such as teachers, students, and the school environment.

From the F-test, the analysis of variance results yielded an F-calculated value (Fhitung) of 47.593. This value is greater than the F-table value (Ftabel) with the degrees of freedom for the numerator, k (number of independent variables) = 1, and the degrees of freedom for the denominator, $n-k = 57-1 = 56$, which is 4.00. Thus, $F\text{-calculated} \geq F\text{-table}$, or $47.593 > 4.00$, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) that there is no relationship, and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis (H_a) that there is a relationship. Therefore, the research hypothesis proposed by the author is accepted, indicating a positive and significant effect of the availability of school facilities and infrastructure on the learning services at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung. Consequently, as the availability of facilities and infrastructure at the school increases, the quality of learning services at the school also improves.

Conclusions and Recommendation

Conclusions

The availability of facilities and infrastructure is defined as all the equipment, tools, and resources that directly support and facilitate the implementation of the learning process. The indicators for the variable of school facilities and infrastructure availability include the availability of teaching tools, learning media, classrooms, a library, a science laboratory, and play/sports areas.

Learning services refer to the efforts made by teachers to provide satisfaction in learning services to educational customers (students) through actions or activities that emphasize the quality of the learning interaction. The indicators for the learning services variable include the reliability of teachers in delivering learning services, teachers' responsiveness in providing learning services, the assurance of service quality in learning, and empathy in learning services.

The research results indicate that from the hypothesis testing, the calculated F value (Fhitung) is greater than the F-table value (Ftabel), specifically $47.593 > 4.00$, leading to the acceptance of the research hypothesis. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant effect of the availability of school

facilities and infrastructure on the learning services at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung, amounting to 46.4%.

Recommendation

Based on the results of the conducted research, the author offers the following recommendations:

1. For the School

The school should enhance the quality of its services by upgrading and equipping its facilities and infrastructure to improve learning services. In line with the highest scoring items, the school should maintain and further increase the availability of facilities and infrastructure. Specifically, the school should provide appropriate whiteboards and markers, place the library in an easily accessible location within the school, and ensure that tables and chairs are available for students during science practicals. In response to the lowest scoring items, the school should also provide cleaning tools, such as brooms and trash bins. Regarding the highest scoring indicators, the school should continue to prioritize and improve the availability of teaching tools. Meanwhile, in relation to the lowest scoring indicators, the school should focus on enhancing the availability of play and sports areas.

2. For Teachers

Teachers are encouraged to maintain and further improve their learning services through the availability of facilities and infrastructure at SMP Negeri 4 Tarutung. Teachers should ensure mastery of the subject matter so that it can be easily understood by students. Additionally, it is important for teachers to feel satisfied with conducting lessons according to the scheduled timetable. In line with the highest scoring indicators, teachers should maintain and further enhance their satisfaction with the availability of facilities and infrastructure, particularly regarding their reliability in delivering learning services. On the other hand, in response to the lowest scoring indicators, teachers should focus on maximizing their satisfaction with the availability of facilities and infrastructure related to the assurance of service quality in learning.

3. For Future Researchers

Future researchers who wish to study learning services are advised to explore other variables that may influence learning services. Additionally, those interested in examining the effects of the availability of school facilities and infrastructure should consider connecting it with other variables, as it may potentially impact other aspects related to the availability of these resources.

Bibliography

1. Arikunto. (2010). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
2. Ariawan, S. (2020). *Building Critical Thinking in Covid-19 Pandemic Era: Impossible or I am Possible? International Research Journal on Advanced Science Hub* (Vol. 2). Retrieved from www.rspsciencehub.com
3. Al Wahiba, Kholida. M. (2014) "Pengaruh Kelengkapan Sarana Dan Prasarana Terhadap Minat Belajar Siswa Kelas

- Viii Di Mts Ma'arif Karang Trenggalek". (Skripsi Sarjana, UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim)
4. Azan, Khairul. (2015). Mutu Layanan Akademik, *Jurnal Administrasi Pendidikan* 12(1), 190-203
 5. Azizah, Nurul. (2020). Pengaruh Dimensi Kualitas Pelayanan terhadap Kepuasan Siswa di MTS Mathla'ul Anwar Seribu Pesawaran, *Economic Education And Entrepreneurship Journal*. 3(1), 31-38
 6. Aznan, Muhammad. R. (2022) "Pengaruh Manajemen Sarana dan Prasarana Terhadap Kualitas Layanan Pembelajaran di Sekolah Menengah Atas Negeri 1 Kampar", (Skripsi Sarjana, UIN Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau)
 7. Bararah, Isnawardatul. (2020). Pengelolaan Sarana dan Prasarana Pendidikan Dalam Meningkatkan Kualitas Pembelajaran. *Jurnal MUDDARISUNA*, 10(2), 351-370
 8. Darmawan, Bambang. (2016). "Pengaruh Layanan Pembelajaran, Sarana-Prasarana, Kerjasama, Institusi, dan Pemasaran Lulusan Terhadap Kepuasan Siswa". *Jurnal administrasi pendidikan*. 13(1), 141-167
 9. Dewi, Titik. P. (2021). Ketersediaan Tempat Bermain/Berolahraga Di Sekolah Dasar Negeri Se-Kecamatan Demak Kabupaten Demak, *Jurnal Pendidikan Jasmani Kesehatan Dan Rekreasi*, 3(1), 121-129
 10. Eveline & Nara. H. (2018) *Teori Belajar dan Pembelajaran*, (Bogor: Ghalia Indonesia)
 11. Fatmawati, Nur. (2019). "Pemanfaatan dan Pemeliharaan Sarana dan Prasarana Pendidikan". *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan, Keguruan, dan Pembelajaran*, 3(2), 115-121
 12. Fiandi, Y. U., A, M. Sudirman & Noor, Marzuki (2021), Kualitas Layanan Pendidikan Di SMK Muhammadiyah Braja Selabah Lampung Timur. *Jurnal Program Studi Administrasi Pendidikan*, 1(2), 120-127
 13. Habibi, Adib. (2019). Implementasi Manajemen Tatalaksana Pendidikan dalam Meningkatkan Layanan Pembelajaran di Sekolah / Madrasah, *Jurnal agama islam dan ilmu pendidikan*, 2(2), 27-37
 14. Hamzah & Uno. (2009). *Model Pembelajaran Menciptakan Proses Belajar Mengajar yang Kreatif dan Efektif*, (Jakarta: Bumi Aksara)
 15. Hidayanto, Feri. M. (2011) "Pengelolaan Sarana dan Prasarana Pendidikan Sekolah Menengah Pertama Negeri Se-Kecamatan Pengasih Kabupaten Kulon Progo", (Skripsi Sarjana: Fak. Ilmu Pendidikan Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta)
 16. Indrawan, Irijus. (2015). *Pengantar Manajemen Sarana dan Prasarana Sekolah*, (Yogyakarta: Budi Utama)
 17. Khotijah, Siti. (2022) Pengaruh Manajemen Sarana Dan Prasarana Terhadap Peningkatan Kualitas Layanan Pembelajaran Dan Kepuasan Peserta Didik Di Mts Nu Kraksan. *Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*. 2(3), 1-7
 18. Luthiyah, Fitwi. (2016) Manajemen Perpustakaan Dalam Meningkatkan Layanan Perpustakaan, *Jurnal el-Idare*, 1(2), 189-202
 19. Manullang, T., & Silitonga, M. (2022). Determinan Hasil Belajar Anak: Lingkungan Keluarga, Lingkungan Sekolah, dan Lingkungan Masyarakat. *JKKP (Jurnal Kesejahteraan Keluarga dan Pendidikan)*, 9(01), 92-101.
 20. Mauling. (2017). *Pengelolaan Pendidikan*, (Bandung : Pustaka Setia)
 21. Mawey, Thalia Claudia. (2018). Pengaruh Kepercayaan Dan Kualitas Layanan Terhadap Kepuasan Nasabah Pt Bank Sulutgo, *Jurnal EMBA*, 6(3), 1198-1207
 22. Mulyadi. (2019) "Tingkat Kepuasan Siswa Terhadap Layanan Pembelajaran Dan Sarana Belajar Di Sd N Mukiran 03 Tahun Ajaran 2018/2019" (Skripsi Sarjana, Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta)
 23. Nurmadiyah. (2018). "Manajemen Sarana dan Prasarana" dalam *Jurnal Al-Afkar*. 6(1), 30-50
 24. Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan Nasional Republik Indonesia No. 24 Tahun 2007 Tentang Standar Sarana dan Prasarana Untuk Sekolah Dasar/ Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (SD/MI), Sekolah Menengah Pertama/ Madrasah Tsanawiyah (SMP/MTs), dan Sekolah Menengah Atas/ Madrasah Aliyah (SMA/MA)
 25. Peraturan Pemerintah RI No. 57 Tahun 2021 Pasal 25 Tentang Standar Sarana dan Prasarana
 26. Prastyawan. (2016). Manajemen Sarana Dan Prasarana Pendidikan, *Al Hikmah Jurnal Studi Keislaman*. 6(1), 33-46
 27. Rahmawati, Kiki. A. (2019) "Pengaruh Manajemen Sarana dan Prasarana Terhadap Peningkatan Kualitas Layanan Pembelajaran di Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Mojokerto". (Skripsi Sarjana, UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya)
 28. Rokhani, Siti. (2021). Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Dan Kualitas Pembelajaran Daring Terhadap Kepuasan Mahasiswa Dimasa Pandemi Covid-19, *JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT (SME's)*. 14(3), 291-310
 29. Rosmalah, (2022). Hubungan Ketersediaan Sarana dan Prasarana di Sekolah dengan Motivasi Belajar Siswa Kelas V SD, *Jurnal Pendidikan & Pembelajaran Sekolah Dasar*. 1(3), 311-317
 30. Sanjaya, Wina. (2013). *Kurikulum dan Pembelajaran*, (Jakarta : Kencana)
 31. Sinta, Ike. M. (2019). Manajemen sarana dan prasarana. *Jurnal Islamic Education Manajemen*. 4(1). 78-92
 32. Siswadi, Fery. (2018). Pengaruh Kualitas Layanan Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Dan Loyalitas Pelanggan, *Jurnal Pustakawan Indonesia*, 18(1), 42-53
 33. Sopian, Ahmad. (2019). Manajemen Sarana dan Prasarana, *Jurnal Tarbiyah Islamiyah*. 4(2), 43-54
 34. Sudjana, (2011). *Metode Statistik*. (Bandung: Tarsito)
 35. Sukaesih. (2019), Kedisiplinan Guru Dalam Meningkatkan Motivasi Belajar Peserta Didik Pada Sekolah Dasar Negeri, *Journal of education management & administration review*, 3(1), 77-81
 36. Sugiyono, (2016). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*. (Bandung: Alfabeta)
 37. Suyono, (2017). Keterlaksanaan Layanan Pembelajaran Dalam Bimbingan Belajar Oleh Guru Kelas Berdasarkan

- Tanggapan Siswa Di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Sosial, sains, dan Humaniora*, 3(1), 175-184
38. Tim Redaksi Kamus Bahasa Indonesia, (2008), Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (KBBI), (Jakarta ; Pusat Bahasa)
39. Tim redaksi utama. (2019) Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Tentang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional (SISDIKNAS) (Yogyakarta: Laksana)
40. Triyanto Pristiwaluyo. (2014) *Analisis Kualitas Layanan Pembelajaran Fakultas Ilmu Pendidikan Universitas Negeri Makassar*, diakses pada 3 oktober dari <https://osf.io/a8tfz/download>
41. Turahman, Mutia. (2018). *Ketersediaan Sarana dan Prasarana Dalam Meningkatkan Kualitas Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam di SMP Negeri 28 Makassar*. (Skripsi Sarjana, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar)
42. Zalfa, Anastya. (2022). Peranan Lingkungan Sekolah Terhadap Penguatan Karakter Peduli Lingkungan Siswa SMAN 111 Jakarta, *Jurnal Pendidikan Sosiologi Dan Humaniora*, 13(2), 835-841
43. Zainiyati, Husniatus. (2017). *Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Berbasis ICT*, (Jakarta: Kencana)
44. Zohriah, Anis. (2015). Analisis Standar Sarana Dan Prasarana, *TARBAWI*, 1(2), 53-62